

Khwāja Hasan Nizāmī’s “Krishna-Biti”

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Khwaja Hasan Nizami (1873-1955) grew up among the custodians of one of the major Sufi institutions in India, the Nizamuddin shrine in Delhi. Breaking with his family’s hereditary role of being pilgrim guides and professional petitioners,¹ Nizami became one of the more successful Urdu journalists and writers of the early 20th century. One major theme of his literary output was the vanished glory of the Mughal Empire. He is credited with a vast number of works on a wide variety of subjects,² often pamphlets or articles, as well as novels. In literary circles, he was especially recognized for his popular semi-autobiographical diaries called *Roznamcha*.

In the early twentieth century Urdu came into its own as a prose language. Khwaja Hasan Nizami participated in this development as an innovative stylist, particularly in the fields of biography, autobiography, and diary writing. It is said that his oratorical style and eloquence were shaped by the fact that he went to school with Mughal princes. At the height of his career, he associated with great Urdu literary figures such as, Shibli Nu’mani, Abul Kalam Azad, Akbar Allahabadi,³ and Iqbal.⁴ Nizami also went beyond the book as a literary form by becoming involved in all kinds of journalistic activities, writing articles for Muslim newspapers as well as starting a number of his own religious magazines, for example, *Pir Bha’i* (Brother Disciple) *Darvish* (Dervish), and *Munadi*

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(The Caller). All of his works, including those considered in this article, were originally composed in Urdu. Nizami frequented the princely states as well as the intellectual salons and his portraits of notable personalities of the era grace the pages of his series of diaries, called the *Roznamcha*.

His attitudes to British rule and to Hindu-Muslim co-operation fluctuated during his career. As a good journalist, Nizami seems to have responded quickly to the pulse of Muslim popular opinion.

It is clear that as a twentieth century Sufi in India, Nizami both inherited and fashioned for himself a set of complex representations of Hindus and Hinduism. In his writings one can trace various strands of the historical patterns characterizing the encounter of the two religions and respective civilizations. The idealized image of Muslim Sufis in India, in particular as represented by the Sufis of the Chishti Order, is that of tolerance and openness to spiritual exchange and inter-religious cooperation. Chishtis are considered to be the most “Indianized” of the four main *silsilas* (Sufi orders). This is because the Chishti Sufis were willing in many cases to initiate Hindus as well as other non-Muslims as disciples without the requirement of formal conversion to Islam. The Chishti Order also sanctioned the use of Qawwali music as a spiritual practice in order to reach a broader indigenous audience. This tradition of Sufi music and poetry became one means of translating Islam for the Indian population. In one of his works, *Fatimi Dawat-i Islam*, (The Fatimid Missionary Movement for Islam) Khwaja Hasan Nizami describes the Chishti appropriation of Hindu rituals such as rubbing with sandalwood paste that were transferred from ceremonies surrounding idols to ritual veneration of Sufis saints’ graves.⁵ As part of their openness to more pluralistic or universalist interpretations,

Chishtis were also said to lean towards the monistic mystical Unity of Being (*wahdat al-wujud*), which exhibited more affinity to the “all is one” or “everything is brahman” doctrines of some Indian philosophies. Early Chishtis were said to eschew political activities and court patronage,

although by late Mughal times the Chishti shrines and their custodians seem to have been benefited from court favor and patronage.⁶

An example of the Chishti tolerant approach found in Nizami's writings occurs in one of his most popular books, the *Nizami Bansiri* (The Nizami Reed Flute), a biography of Nizamuddin Auliya (d. 1325) and other Chishti Sufis. Here Nizami claims to make extensive use of a work still in manuscript, "*Char Rozah*", which is supposed to have been written by a medieval Hindu observer, Hardev.⁷ Nizami's account of Hardev's adventures often portrays the Hindu as the sympathetic and sensitive character. For example, in one anecdote a coarse Muslim shopkeeper claims that the Hindu, Hardev, is a dhimmi, (a protected non-Muslim subject under Muslim rule) and therefore under his protection. During a subsequent encounter with the Sufi saint, Nizamuddin Auliya uses his spiritual insight and psychic knowledge of the incident in order to correct the shopkeeper, reminding him that all beings are, in fact, exclusively under the protection of God alone.⁸

Throughout his career Khwaja Hasan Nizami took an interest in other religions. In addition to the writings on Hinduism mentioned in this paper, Nizami wrote favorably about Jesus, the Sikhs⁹ and Baha'ullah, founder of the Baha'i faith.¹¹ It is known from Nizami's writings and autobiographical references that he had embarked as a young man on an extensive study of Hinduism and visits to major Hindu pilgrimage sites.

In 1323/1905 and 1324/1906 Khaksar Sahib's teachings instilled in me a desire to meet Hindu fakirs and visit the Hindu pilgrimage sites. Leaving Delhi, I first went to Mathura and Brindavan and spent some time in the company of the fakirs who lived there. On this trip, my only baggage was a blanket, a bag, and a long-colored shirt. From Mathura I traveled to Ayodhya, Benares, Gaya, Bodhgaya, Hardwar, Rishikesh, and other sites. I visited their famous temple and met some other religious mendicants (fakirs)".¹² Nizami then explains that he subsequently published only a few

anecdotes about this lengthy trip scattered among his various writings. A full book about these experiences that he had written was never published because his opponents within the clan wanted to use his positive interest in Hinduism against him. Nizami did, in fact publish a number of books explaining elements of Hinduism including the biography of Krishna analyzed here as well as a few other books presenting basic Hindu teachings for a Muslim audience.¹³

The image of Muslim Sufis exchanging esoteric knowledge with Hindu yogis is one familiar from Mughal paintings and other literary references. The early travels of Nizami seem to have fulfilled this tradition of inter-religious encounter. One product of this interfaith phase in Nizami's career is his biography of Krishna.

Biography of Krishna (Krishna Biti)

In his preface to the first edition of Krishan Biti or as later editions were titled, Krishan Katha, Nizami characterized the biography of Krishna as the body and soul of Indian life.¹⁴ In general, Nizami liked to utilize the biographical genre as a didactic and realistic form. His portrayal of Krishna is sympathetic, treating Krishna as a historical heroic figure. In the preface he articulates several reasons for undertaking the work.

The first reason cited is his desire to overcoming the problem of certain authors' injecting fantasies and legends into the Krishna story.¹⁵

My aim in composing this treatise is to explain to Muslims the true state of Krishna and to not allow any negative thinking to remain in their minds regarding this past figure since this is against the guidance of Qur'an and shari'a which teach that, "certain thoughts are sins". I think that to consider Krishna, as some ignorant Hindus and worthless Hindu books have portrayed him, as debauched, deceitful, and a trouble-maker, is untrue and a serious sin.¹⁶

While defending Krishna against false accusations, Nizami is at the same time blaming certain Hindu writings for distorting his life story. Throughout the text, Nizami tackles whatever details of the Krishna story

he considers objectionable. A prominent example of this is the sexual innuendo surrounding Krishna's dalliance with the cowgirls (Gopis). Here Nizami is not so much opposed to miracle and myth as to the potentially scandalous elements surrounding the episodes of Krishna's entertainment of the Gopis and his association with Radha. In terms of arguments against erotic understandings of Krishna's association with the Gopis, Nizami notes the improbability of such goings on in the context of the honor codes of the society of the cowherders' village where Krishna lived. In addition, Nizami contends that Krishna was only a child at this time and thus was unlikely to have any romantic or sexual interest in the Gopis. Nizami's recounting of Krishna's life is also careful to deflect any criticisms of Krishna as licentious. At the same time, it demonstrates that a prominent Muslim opponent of politicized aspects of Hinduism, in this case "shuddhi" of the 1920s, could at the same time have written sympathetically about a Hindu religious icon. The Krishna figure and celebration of festivals such as Holi were certainly not alien to the experience of many Indian Muslims. Still, Nizami's deliberate efforts for inter-communal understanding in producing this work suggest his support for a united Indian nation. In fact, a popular perception of Nizami and his successors as being ideal integrated Muslim citizens of India continues until the present.

In his treatise Nizami also felt the need to counter the implication that Radha was Krishna's physical lover. He does so by philosophizing about Radha as indicating a concept rather than a historical female. Thus, she is said to abstractly represent not "an actual flesh and blood female, but the name given to Krishna's attraction to the principle of love ('ishq)" for, according to Nizami, Hindus make images for such feelings and qualities.¹⁷ He explains that the beauty of the spiritual station of love whose manifestation was Krishna was given the name "Radha" while an image (murti) was fashioned to be an embodiment of this spiritual state. In his explanation Nizami also seems to be aiming to counter negative understandings of "idol-worship" on the part of his Muslim readers. For example, his statement that, "Everyone knows that in the olden times

Hindus made images for the divine qualities and through these they would teach people about God's attributes as in the case of the feminine principle," could be understood as an apology for the Hindu use of images in worship.¹⁸ Ironically, Nizami's strategy of treating the worship of diverse images and Gods in Hinduism either by historicizing them, as in the case of Krishna, or by turning them into philosophical principles, as with Radha, is quite similar to that of his Hindu opponents in the Arya Samaj movement. As a scholar of the Arya Samaj has observed, "For the Arya Samaj 'monotheism replaced polytheism . . . only a rationalistic monotheism remained supported by a new reinterpretation of the past'.¹⁹ The Aryas held that only the Vedas were authoritative while later Hindu texts and their contents were distorted aspects of popular religion and myth that had to be explained away. Thus, all forms of personal God-worship and myth were discouraged according to the Arya Samajist perspective.

Nizami uses various strategies in order to convey the concept of Krishna sympathetically to his Muslim audience. Who was his audience? In likelihood it consisted of a Muslim learned elite like himself with the addition of a new group of middle and lower middle class Muslims achieving literacy, or even non-literates who might have the texts read to them. The sophistication of certain of his arguments suggest that these were not so much works of popularization of higher themes to a less educated audience, but rather works of translation of Hindu ideas to Muslims who might have little knowledge of the Hindu religion and its doctrines. In some ways Nizami resembles his Arya Samajist opponents when he writes in the demythologizing mode. In downplaying the idea of Krishna as a distinct personal God, Nizami articulates a perspective compatible with modernist sensibilities among his Indian contemporaries, whether Muslim or Hindu.

In terms of establishing parallels to Muslim religious and theological symbolism, he presents Krishna in this work both as a guide (*hadi*) and avatar. The "guide" idea allows Nizami to invoke elements of the Muslim understanding of prophethood without explicitly calling

Krishna a prophet. Throughout the text, Nizami translates Hindu religious concepts into Muslim religious and political frameworks. Therefore, one observes a certain Islamization of Hindu themes, for example, Krishna is compared to Moses while the Hindu figure of Yashodha, who allowed her infant daughter to be sacrificed in place of Krishna, is compared to that of the Qur'anic heroine 'Asiya, wife of Pharaoh. Nizami notes with regard to Yashodha's heroism and devotion that it is usually women who are the first to heed a new religious mission, in this case as well as in the case of Khadija, wife of Muhammad (pbuh).²⁰ Earlier in the section about Yasudha, he compares her nurturing actions with those of Halima, the Arab tribal woman who nursed the infant Muhammad.²¹ In an odd mixture of theological categories, Nizami asserts that the memory of Yashodha's sacrifice of her child will remain alive until the day of Resurrection (*qiyamat*).²²

The symbolism of Krishna's flute playing and dancing is also interpreted with special consideration of the expectations of a Muslim audience. For Nizami, the flute of Krishna evokes Islamic images such as the famous reed flute of Rumi's Sufi poem, the *Masnavi*, rather than the frivolity of music used purely for entertainment. The imagery of the dancing Krishna provokes the following comment from Nizami:

We Muslims cringe at the mention of dancing but it should make no difference in our respect for Krishna, since such dancing was the custom of the Hindus at this epoch. Everyone, high and low, rich and poor, used to dance, just as today the British and Europeans, from their lower classes up to their royalty, dance together with their wives.²³

In presenting the biography of Krishna, Nizami is playing to a number of audiences. Through the composition of this biography, he is also attempting to forge alliances with groups of sympathetic Hindus in order to constitute a shared Hindu-Muslim Indian identity that could form the basis for social coexistence and political cooperation.

A second objective of the work is stated to be familiarizing

Muslims with Hindus and Hinduism. Nizami establishes his credentials and authority for providing such information.

I have been studying the religious knowledge and society of the Hindus for twenty years and to some extent I have succeeded in understanding their religious and worldly values. By studying their religious sciences, I should not give the impression that I have mastered Sanskrit or perused all of their learned books. Instead, my goal was that I should study the Hindus themselves, their customs and habits, for these are the very books of the Hindus which any person can learn to understand, these are the books of history, religion, mysticism and society. After reading them one is no longer concerned with reading paper books.²⁴

These comments, taken with others in the adjacent sections of the text, indicate a certain ambivalence in the author's appreciation of Hinduism. Nizami provides another reason for the composition of this biography of Krishna—that of serving the cause of the Urdu language. He asserts that it is the shared responsibility of Hindus and Muslims to assist the progress of Urdu, and to keep it alive. Thus, an important subject like the life of Krishna should be treated in Urdu and treated well, and moreover expressed in clear and simple Urdu.

Perhaps the most intriguing reason given by Nizami for preparing the biography of Krishna is the quest for his own identity.

I have studied Hindus in a way that does not require books. I didn't ask for a bibliography of Hindu books. These you will find at the European publishing houses where they have crossed the ocean in order to be printed. I don't claim to be a master of Hindu learning and I only claim that through the Hindus themselves I have studied their religion and world. I took up a staff and blanket travelling to Mathura, Brindavan, and Gokul, staying there for some time. I traced Sri Krishna's life from birth, to childhood, to triumph, to

Haridwar Ayodhya, and Banaras I travelled alone, the earth was my bed and my pillow a stone...Why have I made this investigation? For the reason that I have lived in India for six hundred years, many of my ancestors are buried in this soil, I have ruled this region for hundreds of years. It is now this soil that has come to hold a claim on me, rather than I having a right to it...Islam has told me that 'love of homeland is part of faith'. Thus, why shouldn't I make every effort to see and understand my beloved? My being is constituted by the earth of this land and my prophet has said, 'He who knows himself knows his Lord'.²⁵

The implication of these passages is that by knowing more about Hinduism, Nizami--and ultimately any other Muslim-- will come to know more about himself. Here we find the theme of Hindu Muslim unity established through their mutual association with a place, its soil and history. Nizami thus corrects the negative perception of "dual loyalty" on the part of Indian Muslims by demonstrating their integration into India in both physically embodied and specifically Islamic terms. It should be pointed out that such ideas about the Indianness of Muslims were not alien to Nizami's contemporary Muslim interlocutors, whether among the ulema or more secular Indian Nationalists such as Maulana Abu'l-Kalam Azad. Such discourse might draw on a long Indian Muslim heritage of celebrating the glories of India and the positive references to it in Islamic tradition, for example, praise of India in the works of Azad Bilgrami (d. 1786).²⁶

In the passage cited above, the trope of metonymy guides Nizami's representation of himself as the archetypal Muslim migrant who has been in India for six hundred years. This expression of his identity can be positively read as a willingness to develop from the role of an "outsider" to becoming incorporated into the body of India thereby indicating, at least symbolically, the willingness of all Indian Muslims to acknowledge and embrace the Indian part of their heritage and identity. He is careful not to represent himself as having a right to rule, rather it is

India that ultimately transcends religious identities and rules him. Further, by evoking mystical union Nizami suggests that becoming united with and absorbed by his “beloved” homeland is ultimately a source of self-knowledge and even knowledge of God. In these paragraphs we gain some insight into “the Hindu” as understood by Khwaja Hasan Nizami. We also note that Nizami raises a number of themes current in cultural studies and post-colonial theory, by interrogating the sources and organization of knowledge about the Other. He asserts that his knowledge of Hindus and Hinduism is derived from direct lived experience rather than from bibliographies compiled by the colonizers or books printed in the European metropolises. We can therefore characterize Nizami's position as asserting that “knowledge” requires association with a "living Other" and a “real” Hinduism that is accessible to him as an Indian. The Krishna figure is clearly one that carries an appeal for him, both as a historical human teacher whose activities impart lessons of the highest human moral standards, and as an abstract philosophical ideal that is able to transcend communal identities. He concluded the 1917 edition of the book with a nationalist plea for Hindu Muslim unity and cooperation. “O Indians, now you must forget all the disagreements into which the struggle to rule has plunged us Hindus and Muslims, for now both of us are being ruled by a third party. Now we should become of one body, one mind, one mentality in order to live in this country, and say: Our India is the best in the world”²⁷.

After the introduction, the book begins with a glossary of technical terms from the Hindu religion.⁸¹ The next topic covered is Hindu cosmology, followed by Hindu sacred books, Hindu sects, rituals, and the Hindu concept of time.²⁸ A further section covers the four “G’s”; the cow (ga’o), Ganges (Ganga), Gita, and the Gayatri Mantra.²⁹ Social and practical elements such as caste, pilgrimage sites, and belief in astrology complete the survey of Hinduism.

At the conclusion of Nizami’s overview of Hindu doctrine and practice, an additional brief treatise (20 pp) by Nawab Sir Amin Jang Bahadur on “The Philosophy of the Hindu People” is appended. Overall,

the tenor of the entire work is accommodating and contextualized within an appeal for inter-religious dialogue and harmony. Despite this, the concluding remarks, perhaps unavoidably, obliquely mention the Arya threat and anticipate, “thousands, no hundreds of thousands of Muslims needing to learn Sanskrit and know about Hinduism in order to preserve and propagate their own religion”.³⁰

Conclusion

In conclusion, one may take Khwaja Hasan Nizami’s representations of Hindus and Hinduism as exemplifying some of the currents and tensions expressed in early twentieth century India as communal identities became increasingly charged and polarized.

In terms of the Hindu religion, Nizami’s writings demonstrate that it was possible for a Muslim of his generation to find elements shared with Hindus such as admiration for heroism and sacrifice, or respect for guides and teachers. This idea of promoting common moral and spiritual values is evident in the author’s treatment of Krishna as an exemplary figure. The type of Hindu who was the most accessible to Nizami was the one following bhakti or devotional religion. The biography of Krishna, then, may be seen as representing the Hindu in the tradition of Sufi/ bhakti compatibility and fusion, an articulation of South Asia Islam that appreciates the other and attempts to establish common ground.

The issue of representing Muslim identity in India, however, occasionally became problematic for Nizami since loyalties beyond India are both real and positive for Muslims. Perhaps in response Nizami made the move of tracing the origin of the Aryans to ancient Egypt in his work *Firauni Ta’rikh*,³¹ thereby complicating the myth of Hindu origins in an interesting way. Writing laudatory biographies about Hindu icons such as Krishna and Rama could also be taken as reflecting one Muslim’s response to a disturbing phenomenon of India in the 1920’s, the maligning or insulting of other religion’s leaders and heroes, leading to inflamed communal passions and riots.

Nizami, as a Muslim mystic, straddled both reformist causes and

the tradition of popular devotion to the saints represented by Indian Sufism. Thus, on occasion he made use of some of the same reformist tactics and organs of influence as his primary Hindu rivals in the Arya Samaj. Examples would be the use of the popular press and extensive travel on the new networks of railways. In a new move for a Sufi guide, who traditionally trained disciples through intimate personal contact, Nizami allowed aspiring disciples to sign up for initiation on vouchers printed in the back of some of his publications. While he continued the Sufi tradition in finding commonality with devotional Hindu symbols and practices, the scope of his tolerance stopped short at accepting actual conversion from Islam to Hinduism and thus Nizami became a political activist when opposing the campaign of the Arya Samaj. In this opposition he went further than other nationalist Muslim leaders such as the 'Ali brothers.

In Khwaja Hasan Nizami's writings his attitudes to Hinduism, religiously and politically, can be seen to respond to the changing circumstances in India during the earlier part of the twentieth. Initially he may be observed attempting to broaden the arena of Indian identity so as to make possible a national space shared by Hindus and Muslims. Muslim communal identity politics became more aggressive in response to the onslaught of the Arya campaigns of reconversion and turned the Sufi into a political activist. While the original enemy was British colonialism, a foe that united Hindus and Muslims, the rise of communal politics carried away much of the cooperation forged during the Khilafat movement. Nizami, like many other Muslim leaders, seems to become less trusting of the good intentions of Hindu leadership, including that of Gandhi.

In his autobiography Nizami includes an imaginative section entitled, "the spiritual autobiography", or "*Lahuti Aap Biti*".³² This segment explains both the physical/human (*nasuti*) and spiritual/divine (*lahuti*) aspects of the human condition. Following concepts suggested by the Sufi poet Rumi's verses about the progression of existence through mineral, vegetal, human, and ultimately, angelic realms,³³ Nizami imaginatively details his own process of evolution. In these past

experiences he ascends through successive spheres of existence in the mineral, vegetable, and animal planes, then Nizami proceeds through human history evoking events from Qur'anic tales of the Prophets, to heroes of Islamic history, and finally to the personalities of his own age. Here he identifies with a range of contemporary political figures including Kaiser Wilhelm, Hindenburg, King George of England, Lloyd George, and finally even Gandhi.

Nizami and his spiritual home, the Nizamuddin Dargah, symbolically represent the space of Indian Muslims' transcending communalism and striving for harmony. Nizami, like many others who dreamed of overcoming differences, must have been disappointed with the rise of communalism and the partition of India. At the same time, he was drawn into the controversy over the Shuddhi campaigns in such a way that some observers have primarily construed him as a communal agitator.³³ The presentation here of his writings introducing Hinduism in a positive light to his fellow Muslims may serve to correct this imbalance.

References:

¹ In Urdu, a "Du'a gu". In the culture of Sufi shrines the custodians and purported descendants of the saints are believed to have closer access to him and therefore are often paid to supplicate on behalf of pilgrims.

²By some accounts, as many as five hundred. Mulla Wahidi, Sawanih 'Umri: Khwaja Hasan Nizami (Delhi: Munadi Khwaja Number, 1957), 130.

³Wahidi, Sawanih, 136-145. Allahabadi's side of their correspondence was published by Nizami in Khutut-e Akbar bi-Nam-e Khwaja Hasan Nizami (Delhi: Mahbub al-Matabi', 1953).

⁴Iqbal and Nizami met and exchanged letters on a number of topics, occasionally disagreeing.

⁵ Asghar Ali Engineer, "Muslims Views of Hindus Past and Present" in Religions View Religions: Explorations in Pursuit of Understanding eds. Jerald Gort, Henry Hansen, H. M. Vroom (Amsterdam: Rodopi, 2006), 198-9.

⁶ On the reflection of this in architectural patronage see Catherine Asher, Architecture of Mughal India (New York: Cambridge University Press, 1992), 295.

⁷ He also published this separately under the title, HarDev ka Roznamcha (Hardev's Diary).

⁸ Khwaja Hasan Nizami, Nizami Bansri (New Delhi: Liberty Art Press, 1990), 39-46.

⁹ A chapter in Khwaja Hasan Nizami, Bivi ki Ta'lim (Delhi: Halqa-i Masha'ikh Book Depot, 1924) pp. 172 ff. as well as Sikh Qaum (Batala: Khwaja Press, n. d.). On his views of Sikhism see Yoginder Sikand, "Building Bridges Between Sikhs and Muslims: The Contribution of Khwaja Hasan Nizami", Studies in Inter-Religious Dialogue, 9 (2, 1999): 178-188.

¹⁰ His work, Irani Darvish features a translation of Baha'ullah's "Kitab al-Asrar" and is advertised in Fransisi Darvish ke Malfuzat (Delhi: Muhammad Sadiq, 1915), p. 33. The work is also mentioned in Ap Biti, 79. Nizami is said to have met with 'Abd al-Baha' while in Egypt. Sawanih, 90.

¹² Ap Biti, 60

¹³ For example, Hindu madhhab ki ma'lumat (Delhi: Delhi Printing Works, 1923) is a work presenting basic Hindu teachings.

¹⁴ Krishan biti ba taswir (subtitled "The True and Explained Life Account of India's Famous Avatar, Sri Krishna") (Delhi: Halqa-i Masha'ikh, 1917). The preface to the 1919 and subsequent editions of the work was prepared by Krishan Prasad, a disciple of Nizami who was himself a Hindu who served as Prime Minister under the Nizam of Hyderabad. Krishan Prasad was a patron of Persianate culture, Hindustani music, and a Chishti Sufi.

¹⁵ *Ibid*, 2.

¹⁶ *Ibid*.

¹⁷ Nizami, Krishan Katha (Delhi: Ansari Press, 1941), 72.

¹⁸ *Ibid*. ¹⁹ Kenneth Jones, Arya Dharm: Hindu Consciousness in 19th Century

Punjab, (Berkeley: University of California, 1976), 32.

²⁰ Krishn Katha, 57. ²¹ Ibid, 53. ²² Ibid, 53.

²³ Nizami, Krishan biti ba taswir, 61.

²⁴ For example, in a collection of his own pronouncements on tabligh published in 1926, Nizami includes a number of statements criticizing the Arya Samajists for lack of reverence towards Rama and Krishna. Tablighi Isharaton ka Majmu'a (Delhi: Ibn 'Arabi Karkon, 1926), 73, 102.

²⁵ Ibid.

²⁶ On Indian nationalism among Deobandi ulema see Yoginder Sikand, "The 'United Nationalism' of Maulana Madni" Millia Gazette, 15 (5, 2004). Online at <http://www.milligazette.com/Archives/2004/01-15Aug04-Print-Edition/011508200434.htm> Viewed Nov. 1, 2009. On Azad Bilgrami's representation of India see Carl Ernst "India as a Sacred Islamic Land" in Religions of India in Practice, ed. Donald S. Lopez, Jr. (Princeton: Princeton University Press, 1995), 556-64.

²⁷ Nizami, Krishan Biti, (Delhi: Munshi Kanz Fazl Husain, 1917), 144.

²⁸ Ibid. 8-28.

²⁹ Ibid, 29-34.

³⁰ Ibid, 64.

³¹ Khwaja Hasan Nizami, Firauni Ta'rikh. (Delhi: Lauh-e Mahfuz Urdu Library, 1944), 279-80.

³² Ap Biti, 135-144. Also published separately as Lahuti Ap Biti (Gurdaspur: A'zamiyya Book Depot, 1922).

³³ For example, Gene Thursby, Hindu-Muslim relations in British India: a study of controversy, conflict, and communal movements in northern India 1923-1928 (Leiden: E. J. Brill, 1975), 37